

science and policy
for a healthy future

HORIZON2020 Programme
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Annex 2.1.3 to D7.3

Matrix-specific questionnaires to accompany the sampling of urine and blood

WP 7

Task 7.3

D7.3

Version 2.0

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Table of contents

1	Introduction and Aims	4
2	Questionnaire accompanying the sampling of urine	4
2.1	Notes	6
2.2	General questions regarding the sample itself	7
2.3	Residential environment and home exposures.....	9
2.4	Dietary habits.....	10
2.5	Lifestyles.....	12
2.6	Important when children are the target group.....	16
2.7	Important when toddlers or young children (up to 4 years) are the target group.....	16
2.8	Any other questions	17
3	Questionnaire accompanying the sampling of blood	18
3.1	Notes	20
3.2	General questions regarding the sample itself	21
3.3	Dietary habits.....	22
3.4	Lifestyles.....	24
3.5	Important when toddlers or young children (up to 4 years) are the target group.....	25
3.6	Any other questions	26

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1 Introduction and Aims

When evaluating human samples for exposure with certain substances or substance groups, it can prove useful in some cases to have information available about potential exposure sources of the sample provider directly prior to the point in time where the sample was taken. This means that the questionnaires accompanying the sampling of a matrix (or matrix-specific questionnaires) specifically aim to mostly cover substances with a short half-life.

This difference to the basic questionnaire should be explicitly explained and continuously stressed to the interviewer staff during training.

The HBM4EU matrix-specific questionnaires have been designed to collect a select amount of information concerning individual characteristics of the participants and on different sources and routes of exposure to the 1st-priority substances selected for study (Phthalates/DINCH, Bisphenols, Per-/Polyfluorinated compounds, Flame Retardants, Cd, Cr, PAHs and Aniline family: MOCA), with the aim to characterise as well as possible the level of exposure to these substances (where considered relevant) directly prior (past 24 or 48 hours) to the sampling.

As urine and blood are currently the most likely matrices to be analysed, questionnaires have been prepared accordingly. It might be necessary to adapt some wording and use specific questions in the urine questionnaire depending on the type of urine envisioned to be sampled (e.g. morning urine, spot urine, etc.).

Furthermore, questions might need to be adjusted or taken out according to the individual study design, e.g. in case there is only one label on the sample container, the questions pertaining to the labelling need to be merged.

Specific testing of these questionnaires in a subsample of a population still needs to be undertaken. It could be feasible to perform testing with representatives (or a subsample) of the envisaged group of participants right before a study using this questionnaire is conducted.

2 Questionnaire accompanying the sampling of urine

In the following, the questionnaire accompanying the sampling of urine is presented.

The notes under Section 2.1 are important to consider when applying the questionnaire. The accompanying Interviewer Manual can be used to learn about the background of questions, the substance groups of interest in each question as well as specific notes and advice for the application of the questions.

QUESTIONNAIRE TO ACCOMPANY THE SAMPLING OF URINE (1st PRIORITY SUBSTANCES)

QUESTIONNAIRE INFORMATION

ID (PARTICIPANT)	_ _ _ _ _ _ _
ID (INTERVIEWER)	_ _ _ _ _ _ _
DATE OF THE INTERVIEW	_ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _
START TIME	_ _ : _ _
END TIME	_ _ : _ _
PLACE	

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2.1 Notes

Questions with a white background are to be addressed to and answered by the participant.

Questions with a grey background are to be answered by the interviewer or the study centre and should not be addressed directly to the participant.

Questions with a light green background are to be asked only when first morning urine is collected.

Questions with a light red background **only have to be asked if (a) urine sampling is not foreseen** in the survey **or** if (b) blood and urine sampling did not happen at the same time (**> 1 h between sampling of blood and sampling of urine**).

2.2 General questions regarding the sample itself

U1 Has the [first morning] urine sample been delivered?

Yes Please continue with question 2.

No Please indicate the reason for missing submission of the morning urine sample below:

a) Sampling was forgotten in the morning [if foreseen: another appointment can be made now]

b) Sampling container not available [if foreseen: another appointment can be made now]

c) No consent

d) Other reason, that being: _____

U2 Was the urine sample collected in the provided container?

Yes

No ► [It should be decided by the study owner if the sample will be discharged or kept. This information should be recorded.]

Questions U3 and U4 can be merged if it is foreseen to use only one label:

U3 Is there a sampling label on the container?

Yes

No ► Please add one to the container now.

U4 Is there a label with the correct participant ID on the container?

Interviewer: Please cross-check label and title pages of all questionnaires asked.

Yes

No ► Please add one to the container now.

U5 When was the [morning] urine sample obtained?

Interviewer: Ask participant or copy from sampling label if this information is included. Please check the information for plausibility! If the date is different to the date of the home visit, please note this down. The sample might have to be discarded.

on 20 at : hrs
 Day Month Year Hour Minute

U6 Is it really the first urine after waking up?

Interviewer: If the time of the sampling is not in the hours of the morning, meaning up to a max. 12 pm, ask the participant(s) whether this time is correct and whether it is really the first urine after waking up.

Yes

No [It should be decided by the study owner if the sample will be discharged or kept. This information should be recorded.]

Don't know ► [It should be decided by the study owner if the sample will be discharged or kept. This information should be recorded.]

Refused ► [It should be decided by the study owner if the sample will be discharged or kept. This information should be recorded.]

U7 When was your last meal before urine sample collection?

Interviewer: Please consider also small snacks like fruit and sweets.

on 20 at : hrs
 Day Month Year Hour Minute

U8 When did you last urinate before urine sample collection?

Interviewer: Ask participant or copy from sampling label if this information is included. Please check the information for plausibility!

on 20 at : hrs
 Day Month Year Hour Minute

Don't know Refused

U9 According to your information, the last visit to the toilet was at least 4 hours before sampling!

Interviewer: Check whether this is plausible and if not, ask all information again.

Yes

No ► [It should be decided by the study owner if the sample will be discharged or kept. This information should be recorded.]

U10 How was the sample stored at home before collection?

Refrigerator

Other cool place

Non-chilled

Don't know Refused

U11 should only be included if the study is foreseen to use containers big enough to collect all morning urine:

U11 Is the morning urine sample complete? Complete means that all morning urine was collected for the urine sample!

Yes

No Please indicate the reason for incomplete morning urine sample:

a) Forgot that all morning urine is collected [if foreseen: another appointment can be made now]

b) Something went wrong [if foreseen: another appointment can be made now]

c) The collection container was too small

d) Other reason, that being: _____

Don't know Refused

2.3 Residential environment and home exposures

U12 Have you been outdoors (walking, cycling, etc.) next to a street with constant traffic during the 24 hours prior to sampling?

No Please continue with question U13.

Yes ► Go to question U12a.

U12a How long in total have you been outdoors (walking, cycling, etc.) next to a street with constant traffic during the 24 hours prior to sampling?

a) Less than 30 minutes

b) Between 30 minutes and 1 hour

c) Between 1 and 4 hours

d) More than 4 hours

Don't know Refused

U13 Have you inhaled smoke from the following energy sources inside your home during the 24 hrs prior to sampling?

Gas

Charcoal/Coal

Wood (firewood, chips, pellets, etc.)

Don't know Refused

Jelly candies	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Smoked food (e.g. ham, smoked pork, smoked cheese, Frankfurters)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Grilled food (over open flame / burning embers)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Fried food	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Toasted bread	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Fast food	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Canned food	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Ready meals (in plastic packaging)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
					Refused	<input type="checkbox"/>

U15 During the past 24 hrs prior to sampling, did you drink beverages from any of the following materials?

Interviewer: It is possible to tick more than one box in the list below. All beverages are asked for, including water, hot drinks and alcoholic drinks.

- | | |
|-------------------|--------------------------|
| Glass bottle | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| Plastic bottle | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| Can | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| Plastic mug | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| Plastic glass | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| Polystyrene | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| Cardboard | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| None of the above | <input type="checkbox"/> |

U16 Before providing the sample, when did you last drink any beverages belonging to the following list?

	Not at all	Less than 12 hours	Between 12 and 24 hours	Between 24 and 48 hours	More than 48 hours ago	Don't know
Sakè	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Beer	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Red wine	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Barley coffee	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Juice (vegetable or fruit)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Whole milk	<input type="checkbox"/>					
					Refused	<input type="checkbox"/>

U17 Did you eat fast food in the past 24 hrs prior to sampling?

Interviewer: Fast foods are processed foods that are easily prepared and served quickly in snack bars and restaurants, typically packed to be 'to-go'.

No Please continue with question U18.

Yes ► Go to question U17a.

U17a How was the fast food packed that you ate during the past 24 hrs prior to sampling?

Interviewer: It is possible to tick more than one box in the list below.

- a) No convenience food at all
- a) In cardboard box
- b) In paper (e.g. bag, box, cup)
- c) In plastic (e.g. bag, box, cup)
- d) In polystyrene foam (e.g. box, cup)
- e) In aluminium container (e.g. canned food)

2.5 Lifestyles

U18 Have you been exposed to tobacco smoke during the 24 hrs prior to sampling?

No

Yes, I have smoked Please continue with question U18a.

Yes, I have been exposed to second hand smoke (passive smoking) Please continue with question U18b.

U18a How many cigarettes during the 24 hrs prior to sampling?

1-5

6-10

11 or more

Refused

U18b How long have you been exposed to second hand smoking during the 24 hrs prior to sampling?

Less than an hour

More than 1 hour

More than 4 hours

Body care products (e.g. body lotion, perfume, shower gel, deodorant)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Sun cream (sunscreen)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
					Refused	<input type="checkbox"/>

U22 Did you take any of the following types of medication during the past 24 hrs prior to sampling?

	Not at all	Less than 5 hours	Between 5 and 12 hours	Between 12 and 24 hours	Don't know
Paracetamol (analgesic)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Any medication in pill or capsule form	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
					Refused <input type="checkbox"/>

U23 During the past 24 hrs prior to sampling, did you undergo one or more of the following medical treatments?

Donated blood

Dialysis

Don't know Refused

U24 In the past 24 hrs prior to sampling, did you put things made out of plastic material (e.g. pens, toys) in your mouth to chew on?

Yes

No

Don't know Refused

in glass jars with
metal lids

Refused

2.8 Any other questions

U28 Were there any peculiarities with the sample or participant's answers?

No

Yes which ones? _____

Don't know Refused

3 Questionnaire accompanying the sampling of blood

In the following, the questionnaire accompanying the sampling of blood is presented.

The notes under Section 3.1 are important to consider when applying the questionnaire. The accompanying Interviewer Manual can be used to learn about the background of questions, the substance groups of interest in each question as well as specific notes and advice for the application of the questions.

QUESTIONNAIRE TO ACCOMPANY THE SAMPLING OF BLOOD (1st PRIORITY SUBSTANCES)

QUESTIONNAIRE INFORMATION	
ID (PARTICIPANT)	_ _ _ _ _ _ _
ID (INTERVIEWER)	_ _ _ _ _ _ _
DATE OF THE INTERVIEW	_ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _
START TIME	_ _ : _ _
END TIME	_ _ : _ _
PLACE	

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3.1 Notes

Questions with a white background are to be addressed to and answered by the participant.

Questions with a grey background are to be answered by the interviewer or the study centre and should not be addressed directly to the participant.

Questions with a light green background are to be asked only when first morning urine is collected.

Questions with a light red background **only have to be asked if (a) urine sampling is not foreseen** in the survey **or** if (b) blood and urine sampling did not happen at the same time (**> 1 h between sampling of blood and sampling of urine**).

3.2 General questions regarding the sample itself

B1 Has the blood sample been taken?

Yes

No Please indicate the reason for missing submission of the blood sample below:

a) Sampling was spontaneously refused

b) Unsuccessful puncture

c) No consent

d) Other reason, that being: _____

B2 When was the blood sample obtained?

on 20 at : hrs
Day Month Year Hour Minute

B3 When was your last meal before blood sample collection?

Interviewer: Please consider also small snacks like fruit and sweets.

on 20 at : hrs
Day Month Year Hour Minute

B4 What total amount was sampled?

Gross volume: . mL

B5 If the gross volume was taken in sub-samples: How many sub-samples were taken?

	Amount	Volume taken in each sub-sample
Small tubes	<input type="text"/> <input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> . <input type="text"/> mL
Large tubes	<input type="text"/> <input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> . <input type="text"/> mL

Questions B6 and B7 can be merged if it is only foreseen to use one label

B6 Is there a sampling label on the container?

Yes

No Please add one to the container now.

B7 Is there a label with the correct participant ID on the container?

Interviewer: Please cross-check label and title pages of all questionnaires asked.

Yes

No Please add one to the container now.

3.3 Dietary habits

If the participant has not eaten in the past 48 hrs (see response to B3 and B3a), B9 can be skipped.

B9 Before providing the sample, when did you last eat any food belonging to the following food groups?

	Not at all	Less than 12 hours	Between 12 and 24 hours	Between 24 and 48 hours	More than 48 hours ago	Don't know
Fish and seafood (e.g. salmon, tuna, snapper, crustaceans like lobster, shellfish like oysters, mussels etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Meat (e.g. white and red meat, game, offal)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Eggs	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Cereals (e.g. bread, crackers, grains, pasta, rice)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Vegetables (e.g. basil, potatoes, carrots, leafy vegetables)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Fruit (e.g. basil, potatoes, carrots, fresh tomatoes, leafy vegetables)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Popcorn (microwave)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Popcorn (home-made)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Peanuts	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Canned food	<input type="checkbox"/>					
					Refused	<input type="checkbox"/>

B10 During the past 24 hrs prior to sampling, did you drink beverages from any of the following materials?

Interviewer: It is possible to tick more than one box in the list below. All beverages are asked for, including water, hot drinks and alcoholic drinks.

- e) Plastic bottle
- f) Can
- g) Plastic mug
- h) Plastic glass
- i) None of the above

If the participant has not eaten in the past 48 hrs (see response to B3 and B3a), B11 can be skipped.

B11 When was the last time you ate dishes from communal catering such as from a canteen, dining hall or cafeteria (e.g. at nursery, school or at work/training pace) prior to providing the blood sample?

Yesterday (1 day ago)	The day before yesterday (2 days ago)	More than 2 days ago or Never	Don't know
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
		Refused <input type="checkbox"/>	

B12 Before providing the sample, when did you last drink any beverages belonging to the following list?

	Not at all	Less than 12 hours	Between 12 and 24 hours	Between 24 and 48 hours	More than 48 hours ago	Don't know
Sakè	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Beer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Red wine	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Barley coffee	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Juice (vegetable or fruit)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Whole milk	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
					Refused <input type="checkbox"/>	

B13a Did you wear personal protection equipment (e.g. a facemask) during one or more of the above-mentioned activities?

Yes

No

Refused

B14 When did you last use any of the following personal care products in the past 48 hours prior to sampling?

	Not at all	Less than 12 hours	Between 12 and 24 hours	Between 24 and 48 hours	More than 48 hours ago	Don't know
Cosmetics (e.g. make-up, nail polish)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Sun cream (sunscreen)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
					Refused	<input type="checkbox"/>

3.5 Important when toddlers or young children (up to 4 years) are the target group

B15 Did you use any of the following toddler foods during the 24 hrs prior to sampling?

	Not at all	Less than 5 hours	Between 5 and 12 hours	Between 12 and 24 hours	More than 24 hours ago	Don't know
Liquid milk formula (ready to feed)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Liquid milk formula (concentrate)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Toddler foods (desserts, fruits, meats, vegetables) in glass jars with metal lids	<input type="checkbox"/>					
				Refused	<input type="checkbox"/>	

3.6 Any other questions

B16 Were there any peculiarities with the sample or participant's answers?			
No	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>	which ones?	_____
		Don't know	<input type="checkbox"/>
		Refused	<input type="checkbox"/>